

The influence of romantic dominance on attitudes toward divorce of selected college students in the Philippines

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Abstract

In 2022, Philippine Senator Robin Padilla filed a bill to legalize divorce in the country. The bill lists 11 grounds for the filing of divorce in court. The objective of this study was to explore the degree of acceptability of these proposed divorce grounds from the viewpoint of selected college students. Based on the bill, the Philippine Divorce Attitude Questionnaire (PDAQ), a researcher-made, 5-point Likert scale questionnaire was created. In addition, the Dominance Scale was used to determine the respondents' attitudes toward dominating a romantic relationship. Furthermore, the study attempted to determine whether a connection exists between the respondents' PDAQ scores and their dominance scale scores. 157 college students from a school in Cainta, Rizal, Philippines volunteered to take part in this study. The PDAQ yielded total weighted means that had verbal interpretations of agree, irrespective of sex or presence of a romantic partner. Based on the PDAQ scores, in general the respondents agree to the divorce grounds laid down by the aforementioned senate bill. With respect to dominance, the respondents' total weighted mean for the subscale of authority found that the respondents were non-authoritative. As for the dominance subscale of disparagement, the respondents' total weighted means found that they were non-disparaging. However, for the dominance subscale of restrictiveness, the respondents' total weighted means showed that they were restrictive irrespective of sex or presence of a romantic partner. Furthermore, an extremely statistically significant difference between the responses of those with and without a romantic partner with respect to Dominance Disparagement subscale scores was established. Pearson r was computed between the respondents' PDAQ scores and their dominance subscale scores in authority, restrictiveness and disparagement. A significant moderate inverse relationship was found between the respondents' PDAQ and Dominance Authority subscale scores. This implies that for the respondents of this study, as their Dominance Authority subscale scores increase, their PDAQ scores moderately decrease and vice versa. In addition, a significant low inverse relationship between the respondents' PDAQ and their Dominance Disparagement subscale scores was also established. In turn, this implies that for the respondents of this study, as their Dominance Disparagement subscale scores increase, their PDAQ scores slightly decrease and vice versa.

Keywords: Divorce in the Philippines; Attitudes toward Divorce; Effects of Divorce; Dominance Scale

1. Introduction

Recently elected Philippine Senator Robin Padilla began his 6-year term of office on June 30, 2022. Padilla, who garnered 26.6 million votes, topped that year's senatorial elections¹.

Among his first acts as senator, Padilla filed a bill legalizing divorce in the Philippines. Under this bill, a petition may be filed for divorce for any of the following grounds:

- The husband or wife is unable to fulfill his/her obligation in the marriage,

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- There exist irreconcilable differences between both parties,
- Annulment was sought abroad by the parties,
- Any of the spouses is presumed dead in accordance with the Civil Code of the Philippines,
- A party is convicted of violating the "Anti-Violence Against Women and Their Children Act",
- One spouse has made an attempt on the life of their child or the petitioner,
- Having children outside the marriage with the following exceptions: if both agree to have a child through IVF or analogous procedure; or after being raped, the wife bears a child,
- Grounds exist for annulling the marriage as provided in the Family Code of the Philippines,
- Repeated abuses directed towards the petitioner or his/her child,
- Both parties have been residing separately for two years at the time the petition was filed and
- The couple has undergone legal separation under the Family Code of the Philippines².

Article 15 of the 1987 Philippine Constitution declares in Section 1 that "The State recognizes the Filipino family as the foundation of the nation. Accordingly, it shall strengthen its solidarity and actively promote its total development."³ However in 2018, Representative Edcel Lagman said that the enactment of a law allowing absolute divorce is not prohibited by the Constitution. He stated further that the 1986 Constitutional Commission did not explicitly say that Congress is precluded from legalizing absolute divorce⁴.

Recently, the Philippine judiciary through the Supreme Court has declared that divorce may be recognized in the Philippines when it is obtained by a Filipino from a foreign spouse and granted by a court abroad⁵. In addition, under the Code of Muslim Personal Laws which was enacted under Presidential Decree by Ferdinand Marcos, Sr in 1977, divorce is allowed as a right of both husband and wife⁶. In effect, there are separate laws in the Philippines for Muslims and non-Muslims with respect to the issue of divorce.

Concerning the status of marriages from a global perspective, it has been observed that

- 1. Marriages are becoming increasingly less common,
- 2. People are marrying later in life across most countries,
- 3. Instead of marriage, couples are ever more engaging in cohabitation,
- 4. Single parenting has been increasing across the world,
- 5. Same-sex marriage was originally legalized in the Netherlands and has been adopted by at least 30 countries since then,
- 6. Depending on the country, a general upward trend in divorce rates has been observed,
- 7. And for younger cohorts, divorce rates appear lower⁷.
- 8. As of 2022, it has been observed that the countries with the highest divorce rates are the following in descending order:
 - (1) Russia,
 - (2) Guam,
 - (3) Moldova,
 - (4) Belarus,
 - (5) Latvia,
 - (6) Ukraine,
 - (7) Lithuania,
 - (8) Kazakhstan,
 - (9) Cuba and
 - (10) Georgia.

As for divorce rates according to major religion, Protestant ranks first with 34%, Muslim with 31%, Jewish with 30%, Catholicism with 21%, Buddhism with 10% and Hinduism with 1%. The following are the most common reasons why divorce occurs,

- (1) Lack of commitment with 73%,
- (2) Excessive arguing with 56%,
- (3) Infidelity with 55%,
- (4) Marrying too young with 46%,
- (5) Unrealistic expectations at 45%,

- (6) Lack of equality in the relationship with 44%,
- (7) Lack of preparation of marriage with 41% and
- (8) Domestic violence or abuse with 25%⁸.

There are only 2 countries in the world that do not allow divorce, which includes the Philippines and the Vatican. In the US, a 2022 survey found that only 15% of adults favor “no-fault” divorce, wherein there is no need for fault by either spouse to be proven before filing for divorce, 30% of US adults aged 18-24 believe that divorce should never be allowed, 12.4% are against marriage and 10% do not believe in marriage at all⁹.

People who undergo divorce can go through five psychological stages. Stage 1 is blaming the spouse and disillusionment. This is characterized by the divorce initiator experiencing negative self-image, stored anger and guilt feelings, while the divorce receiver may experience disbelief, denial, loss of control, fear of the unknown and feelings of shock. Stage 2 is mourning the loss and expression of dissatisfaction, which involves profound painful feeling of grief, hopelessness, a meaningless tortured life, extreme sensitivity, intense preoccupation and difficulty focusing on tasks and loss of parenting role. Stage 3 is anger and resentment which may manifest in rage, feeling of being betrayed, and anger towards the entire opposite sex. The initiator makes himself or herself believe that the other partner is at fault and deserves to suffer. Stage 4 is being single and a firm decision to divorce, which is characterized by freedom-seeking, trying new experiences, self-confidence building and a gradual return to one's roles. Stage 5 is new beginning and acting on the decision, which may include settling down, self-orientation, taking control, final acceptance of the divorce and making new and long-term plans¹⁰.

However, the former spouses are not the only ones affected by the divorce. Their children suffer as well. **Young children** often struggle to comprehend why they must travel back and forth between two homes. They may worry that if their parents can cease loving each other that someday, their parents may cease loving them. Grade school children may become anxious that the divorce is their fault and believe that they misbehaved or did something unacceptable. Teenagers may express anger about the divorce and the changes that ensue as a result. They may tend to blame one or both parents for the disruption of their family lives¹¹.

Divorce may elevate the risk of mental health issues in children regardless of age, gender or culture. In some children, divorce triggers an adjustment disorder as well as higher rates of anxiety and depression. Conduct disorders, delinquency and impulsive behavior are also more prevalent among children of divorced couples. Adolescents of divorced parents are increasingly more susceptible to risky behavior such as substance abuse and early sexual activity¹¹.

Since lack of equality in the relationship has been found to be the top 6th reason for divorce⁸, dominance by one partner over the other appears to be the factor behind this. When couples fight and finally break up, they do so over apparently trivial issues. Obviously, it's not differences over the dinner menu that bring a couple to the verge of divorce. It's the disagreements over who is in charge and who isn't, and the strain and disturbance that result from these disagreements. Couples with unresolved dominance may last for a time. Couples may even stay together forever, but their relationship is fundamentally unstable¹².

Dominance in a relationship can become unhealthy when

- (1) You are unable to expect privacy and the dominant partner believes they own you and look at your devices,
- (2) Your partner exhibits needless jealousy of your accomplishments fearing you might leave them because you have surpassed them,
- (3) There is no acceptance of your refusal and have no respect for your prior engagements and demand complete submission from you but cannot reciprocate the same treatment,
- (4) They judge the people around you whether they be family or friends and they further declare that everyone you know is stupid,
- (5) You become the person at fault for everything bad that befalls the dominant partner,
- (6) They become overly possessive and won't let you use make up or revealing clothes,
- (7) You can't be yourself freely because the tiniest things anger them and you resort to being quiet to avoid becoming emotionally abused by them,
- (8) They expect you to care for them perfectly and will manipulate you or make you feel guilty for not doing things as they wish,
- (9) They act as the “important partner” and make you feel inferior,

- (10) Your partner will dismiss your feelings verbally or non-verbally, which will make you feel that you're always wrong and undeserving of their love¹³.

In view of the foregoing, this study sought to address the following research questions:

- What are the respondents' levels of agreement to the divorce grounds as measured by the Philippine Divorce Attitude Questionnaire when grouped according to
 - Sex;
 - With or without romantic partner?
- What are the respondents' Dominance Authority subscale scores when grouped according to
 - Sex;
 - With or without romantic partner?
- What are the respondents' Dominance Restrictiveness subscale scores when grouped according to
 - Sex;
 - With or without romantic partner?
- What are the respondents' Dominance Disparagement subscale scores when grouped according to
 - Sex;
 - With or without romantic partner?
- Is there a relationship between the respondents' Philippine Divorce Attitude Questionnaire scores and their
 - Dominance Authority subscale scores;
 - Dominance Restrictiveness subscale scores;
 - Dominance Disparagement subscale scores?

2. Material and methods

The respondents were 157 college students from a school in Cainta, Rizal, Philippines who volunteered to take part in this study. The Philippine Divorce Attitude Questionnaire, a 10-item, 5-point Likert scale researcher-made instrument was created based mostly on the grounds for divorce laid down by the Senate bill sponsored by Philippine Senator Robin Padilla². This questionnaire was administered on the respondents to measure their level of agreement to the proposed grounds for divorce. On the other hand, the Dominance Scale¹⁴, a 32-item, 4-point Likert scale instrument was utilized to measure the respondents' level of dominance in three subscales, namely

- Authority with 12 items,
- Restrictiveness with 9 items and
- Disparagement with 11 items.

3. Results

The following tables present the data gathered and the statistical treatments used.

Table 1 Scale of Interpretation for Philippine Divorce Attitude Questionnaire Item Weighted Means

Range	Verbal Interpretation
1.000 – 1.800	Strongly disagree
1.801 – 2.600	Disagree
2.601 – 3.400	Neutral
3.401 – 4.200	Agree
4.201 – 5.000	Strongly agree

Table 2 Attitudes toward Divorce Item Weighted Means: Male Respondents

	Item	Male N=85	Verbal Interpretation
1	1. There should be divorce when the husband or wife cannot fulfill his/her obligation in the marriage	3.047	Neutral
2	2. There should be divorce when both parties in the marriage have irreconcilable differences	3.259	Neutral
3	3. There should be divorce when the marriage was annulled abroad	3.200	Neutral
4	4. There should be divorce when the husband or wife is presumed dead in accordance with applicable laws.	3.377	Neutral
5	5. There should be divorce if one in the couple is convicted of violating the Anti-Violence Against Women and Their Children Act	4.035	Agree
6	6. There should be divorce when there is an attempt by a parent on the life of the child of the couple or on the life of the other spouse	3.847	Agree
7	7. There should be divorce when having children outside the marriage except if both agree to have a child through in vitro fertilization or similar procedure, or if the woman bears a child after being raped	3.235	Neutral
8	8. There should be divorce when there are grounds for annulling the marriage based on the Family Code of the Philippines	3.188	Neutral
9	9. There should be divorce when there are repeated abuses against one spouse or their child	4.224	Strongly agree
10	10. There should be divorce when both parties have been living separately for two years	2.824	Neutral
	<i>Total weighted mean</i>	3.424	Agree

Table 3 Attitudes toward Divorce Item Weighted Means: Female Respondents

	Item	Female N=72	Verbal Interpretation
1	There should be divorce when the husband or wife cannot fulfill his/her obligation in the marriage	3.208	Neutral
2	There should be divorce when both parties in the marriage have irreconcilable differences	3.250	Neutral
3	There should be divorce when the marriage was annulled abroad	3.361	Neutral
4	There should be divorce when the husband or wife is presumed dead in accordance with applicable laws.	3.333	Neutral
5	There should be divorce if one in the couple is convicted of violating the Anti-Violence Against Women and Their Children Act	4.278	Strongly agree
6	There should be divorce when there is an attempt by a parent on the life of the child of the couple or on the life of the other spouse	4.083	Agree
7	There should be divorce when having children outside the marriage except if both agree to have a child through in vitro fertilization or similar procedure, or if the woman bears a child after being raped	3.250	Neutral
8	There should be divorce when there are grounds for annulling the marriage based on the Family Code of the Philippines	3.486	Agree

9	There should be divorce when there are repeated abuses against one spouse or their child	4.542	Strongly agree
10	There should be divorce when both parties have been living separately for two years	2.986	Neutral
	<i>Total weighted mean</i>	3.578	Agree

Table 4 Attitudes toward Divorce Item Weighted Means: Comparison of Male and Female Responses

	Item	Male N=85	Female N=72
1	There should be divorce when the husband or wife cannot fulfill his/her obligation in the marriage	3.047	3.208
2	There should be divorce when both parties in the marriage have irreconcilable differences	3.259	3.250
3	There should be divorce when the marriage was annulled abroad	3.200	3.361
4	There should be divorce when the husband or wife is presumed dead in accordance with applicable laws.	3.377	3.333
5	There should be divorce if one in the couple is convicted of violating the Anti-Violence Against Women and Their Children Act	4.035	4.278
6	There should be divorce when there is an attempt by a parent on the life of the child of the couple or on the life of the other spouse	3.847	4.083
7	There should be divorce when having children outside the marriage except if both agree to have a child through in vitro fertilization or similar procedure, or if the woman bears a child after being raped	3.235	3.250
8	There should be divorce when there are grounds for annulling the marriage based on the Family Code of the Philippines	3.188	3.486
9	There should be divorce when there are repeated abuses against one spouse or their child	4.224	4.542
10	There should be divorce when both parties have been living separately for two years	2.824	2.986
	<i>Total weighted mean</i>	3.424	3.578

Table 5 Attitudes toward Divorce Item Weighted Means: Respondents without a Romantic Partner

	Item	Without Romantic Partner N=92	Verbal Interpretation
1	There should be divorce when the husband or wife cannot fulfill his/her obligation in the marriage	3.109	Neutral
2	There should be divorce when both parties in the marriage have irreconcilable differences	3.228	Neutral
3	There should be divorce when the marriage was annulled abroad	3.207	Neutral
4	There should be divorce when the husband or wife is presumed dead in accordance with applicable laws.	3.348	Neutral
5	There should be divorce if one in the couple is convicted of violating the Anti-Violence Against Women and Their Children Act	4.130	Agree

6	There should be divorce when there is an attempt by a parent on the life of the child of the couple or on the life of the other spouse	3.902	Agree
7	There should be divorce when having children outside the marriage except if both agree to have a child through in vitro fertilization or similar procedure, or if the woman bears a child after being raped	3.294	Neutral
8	There should be divorce when there are grounds for annulling the marriage based on the Family Code of the Philippines	3.283	Neutral
9	There should be divorce when there are repeated abuses against one spouse or their child	4.261	Strongly agree
10	There should be divorce when both parties have been living separately for two years	2.837	Neutral
	<i>Total weighted mean</i>	3.460	Agree

Table 6 Attitudes toward Divorce Item Weighted Means: Respondents with Romantic Partner

	Item	With Romantic Partner N=65	Verbal Interpretation
1	There should be divorce when the husband or wife cannot fulfill his/her obligation in the marriage	3.127	Neutral
2	There should be divorce when both parties in the marriage have irreconcilable differences	3.286	Neutral
3	There should be divorce when the marriage was annulled abroad	3.350	Neutral
4	There should be divorce when the husband or wife is presumed dead in accordance with applicable laws.	3.350	Neutral
5	There should be divorce if one in the couple is convicted of violating the Anti-Violence Against Women and Their Children Act	4.159	Agree
6	There should be divorce when there is an attempt by a parent on the life of the child of the couple or on the life of the other spouse	4.047	Agree
7	There should be divorce when having children outside the marriage except if both agree to have a child through in vitro fertilization or similar procedure, or if the woman bears a child after being raped	3.221	Neutral
8	There should be divorce when there are grounds for annulling the marriage based on the Family Code of the Philippines	3.381	Neutral
9	There should be divorce when there are repeated abuses against one spouse or their child	4.524	Strongly agree
10	There should be divorce when both parties have been living separately for two years	2.969	Neutral
	<i>Total weighted mean</i>	3.541	Agree

Table 7 Attitudes toward Divorce Item Weighted Means: Comparison between Respondents with and without a Romantic Partner

	Item	Without Romantic Partner N=92	With Romantic Partner N=65
1	There should be divorce when the husband or wife cannot fulfill his/her obligation in the marriage	3.109	3.127
2	There should be divorce when both parties in the marriage have irreconcilable differences	3.228	3.286
3	There should be divorce when the marriage was annulled abroad	3.207	3.350
4	There should be divorce when the husband or wife is presumed dead in accordance with applicable laws.	3.348	3.350
5	There should be divorce if one in the couple is convicted of violating the Anti-Violence Against Women and Their Children Act	4.130	4.159
6	There should be divorce when there is an attempt by a parent on the life of the child of the couple or on the life of the other spouse	3.902	4.047
7	There should be divorce when having children outside the marriage except if both agree to have a child through in vitro fertilization or similar procedure, or if the woman bears a child after being raped	3.294	3.221
8	There should be divorce when there are grounds for annulling the marriage based on the Family Code of the Philippines	3.283	3.381
9	There should be divorce when there are repeated abuses against one spouse or their child	4.261	4.524
10	There should be divorce when both parties have been living separately for two years	2.837	2.969
	<i>Total weighted mean</i>	3.460	3.5414

Table 8 Attitudes toward Divorce Item Weighted Means: All Respondents Combined

	Item	Combined N=157	Verbal Interpretation
1	There should be divorce when the husband or wife cannot fulfill his/her obligation in the marriage	3.121	Neutral
2	There should be divorce when both parties in the marriage have irreconcilable differences	3.255	Neutral
3	There should be divorce when the marriage was annulled abroad	3.274	Neutral
4	There should be divorce when the husband or wife is presumed dead in accordance with applicable laws.	3.357	Neutral
5	There should be divorce if one in the couple is convicted of violating the Anti-Violence Against Women and Their Children Act	4.147	Agree
6	There should be divorce when there is an attempt by a parent on the life of the child of the couple or on the life of the other spouse	3.955	Agree

7	There should be divorce when having children outside the marriage except if both agree to have a child through in vitro fertilization or similar procedure, or if the woman bears a child after being raped	3.242	Neutral
8	There should be divorce when there are grounds for annulling the marriage based on the Family Code of the Philippines	3.325	Neutral
9	There should be divorce when there are repeated abuses against one spouse or their child	4.369	Strongly agree
10	There should be divorce when both parties have been living separately for two years	2.898	Neutral
	<i>Total weighted mean</i>	3.482	Agree

Table 9 Scale of Interpretation for Dominance Scale Item Weighted Means

Range	Verbal Interpretation
1.000 – 1.750	Strongly disagree
1.751 – 2.500	Disagree
2.501 – 3.250	Agree
3.251 – 4.000	Strongly agree

Table 10 Scale of Interpretation for Total Weighted Means of the Dominance Scale on Authoritative

Range	Verbal Interpretation
1.000 – 1.750	Very non-authoritative
1.751 – 2.500	Non-authoritative
2.501 – 3.250	Authoritative
3.251 – 4.000	Very authoritative

Table 11 Dominance Scale on Authority Item Weighted Means: Male

	Item	Weighted Mean N=85	Verbal Interpretation
3	If my partner and I can't agree, I usually have the final say.	2.441	Disagree
6	I hate losing arguments with my partner.	2.259	Disagree
9	When my partner and I watch TV I hold the remote control.	2.329	Disagree
10	My partner and I generally have equal say about decisions.	1.906	Disagree
11	It would bother me if my partner made more money than I did.	2.029	Disagree
14	Things are easier in my relationship if I am in charge.	2.441	Disagree
15	Sometimes I have to remind my partner of who's boss.	2.012	Disagree
18	Both partners in a relationship should have equal say about decisions.	1.718	Disagree
19	If my partner and I can't agree, I should have the final say.	2.394	Disagree

21	My partner needs to remember that I am in charge.	2.177	Disagree
30	I often tell my partner how to do something.	2.541	Agree
31	I dominate my partner.	2.206	Disagree
	<i>Total weighted mean</i>	2.204	Non-authoritative

Table 12 Dominance Scale on Authority Item Weighted Means: Female

	Item	Weighted Mean N=72	Verbal Interpretation
3	If my partner and I can't agree, I usually have the final say.	2.639	Agree
6	I hate losing arguments with my partner.	2.493	Disagree
9	When my partner and I watch TV I hold the remote control.	2.194	Disagree
10	My partner and I generally have equal say about decisions.	1.931	Disagree
11	It would bother me if my partner made more money than I did.	1.847	Disagree
14	Things are easier in my relationship if I am in charge.	2.375	Disagree
15	Sometimes I have to remind my partner of who's boss.	1.938	Disagree
18	Both partners in a relationship should have equal say about decisions.	1.500	Strongly disagree
19	If my partner and I can't agree, I should have the final say.	2.389	Disagree
21	My partner needs to remember that I am in charge.	2.139	Disagree
30	I often tell my partner how to do something.	2.417	Disagree
31	I dominate my partner.	2.174	Disagree
	<i>Total weighted mean</i>	2.170	Non-authoritative

Table 13 Dominance Scale on Authority: Comparison of Males and Females

Welch's t-test		
Group	Male	Female
Mean	2.20441176476	2.16956018515
SD	0.40974526752	0.36587932897
SEM	0.04444311424	0.04311929243
N	85	72
Intermediate values used in calculations: t = 0.5628 df = 154 standard error of difference = 0.062		
P value and statistical significance: The two-tailed P value equals 0.5744 By conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be not statistically significant. Confidence interval: The mean of Male minus Female equals 0.03485157961 95% confidence interval of this difference: From -0.08747670414 to 0.15717986336		

Table 14 Dominance Scale on Authority Item Weighted Means: Without Romantic Partner

	Item	Weighted N=92	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
3	If my partner and I can't agree, I usually have the final say.	2.505		Agree
6	I hate losing arguments with my partner.	2.364		Disagree
9	When my partner and I watch TV I hold the remote control.	2.342		Disagree
10	My partner and I generally have equal say about decisions.	2.033		Disagree
11	It would bother me if my partner made more money than I did.	2.005		Disagree
14	Things are easier in my relationship if I am in charge.	2.364		Disagree
15	Sometimes I have to remind my partner of who's boss.	2.016		Disagree
18	Both partners in a relationship should have equal say about decisions.	1.712		Strongly disagree
19	If my partner and I can't agree, I should have the final say.	2.391		Disagree
21	My partner needs to remember that I am in charge.	2.217		Disagree
30	I often tell my partner how to do something.	2.462		Disagree
31	I dominate my partner.	2.223		Disagree
	<i>Total weighted mean</i>	2.220		Non-authoritative

Table 15 Dominance Scale on Authority Item Weighted Means: With Romantic Partner

	Item	Weighted N=65	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
3	If my partner and I can't agree, I usually have the final say.	2.570		Agree
6	I hate losing arguments with my partner.	2.370		Disagree
9	When my partner and I watch TV I hold the remote control.	2.162		Disagree
10	My partner and I generally have equal say about decisions.	1.754		Disagree
11	It would bother me if my partner made more money than I did.	1.862		Disagree
14	Things are easier in my relationship if I am in charge.	2.477		Disagree
15	Sometimes I have to remind my partner of who's boss.	1.923		Disagree
18	Both partners in a relationship should have equal say about decisions.	1.485		Strongly disagree
19	If my partner and I can't agree, I should have the final say.	2.392		Disagree
21	My partner needs to remember that I am in charge.	2.077		Disagree
30	I often tell my partner how to do something.	2.515		Agree
31	I dominate my partner.	2.146		Disagree
	<i>Total weighted mean</i>	2.144		Non-authoritative

Table 16 Dominance Scale on Authority Comparison of Respondents with and without Romantic Partner

Welch's t-test		
Group	Without Romantic Partner	With Romantic Partner
Mean	2.21965579709	2.14423076929
SD	0.35334305554	0.43439354253
SEM	0.03683856009	0.05387988775
N	92	65
Intermediate values used in calculations: t = 1.1556 df = 119 standard error of difference = 0.065		
P value and statistical significance: The two-tailed P value equals 0.2502 By conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be not statistically significant. Confidence interval: The mean of Without Romantic Partner minus With Romantic Partner equals 0.07542502779 95% confidence interval of this difference: From -0.05381530141 to 0.20466535700		

Table 17 Scale of Interpretation for Total Weighted Means of the Dominance Scale on Restrictiveness

Range	Verbal Interpretation
1.000 – 1.750	Very non-restrictive
1.751 – 2.500	Non-restrictive
2.501 – 3.250	Restrictive
3.251 – 4.000	Very restrictive

Table 18 Dominance Scale on Restrictiveness Item Weighted Means: Male

	Item	Weighted Mean N=85	Verbal Interpretation
2	I try to keep my partner from spending time with opposite sex friends.	2.329	Disagree
4	It bothers me when my partner makes plans without talking to me first.	2.700	Agree
7	My partner should not keep any secrets from me.	3.000	Agree
8	I insist on knowing where my partner is at all times.	2.641	Agree
13	I tend to be jealous.	2.724	Agree
16	I have a right to know everything my partner does.	2.524	Agree
17	It would make me mad if my partner did something I had said not to do.	2.735	Agree
20	I understand there are some things my partner may not want to talk about with me.	1.971	Disagree

32	I have a right to be involved with anything my partner does.	2.441	Disagree
	<i>Total weighted mean</i>	2.563	Restrictive

Table 19 Dominance Scale on Restrictiveness Item Weighted Means: Female

	Item	Weighted Mean N=72	Verbal Interpretation
2	I try to keep my partner from spending time with opposite sex friends.	2.208	Disagree
4	It bothers me when my partner makes plans without talking to me first.	2.722	Agree
7	My partner should not keep any secrets from me.	3.097	Agree
8	I insist on knowing where my partner is at all times.	2.583	Agree
13	I tend to be jealous.	2.792	Agree
16	I have a right to know everything my partner does.	2.563	Agree
17	It would make me mad if my partner did something I had said not to do.	2.896	Agree
20	I understand there are some things my partner may not want to talk about with me.	1.750	Disagree
32	I have a right to be involved with anything my partner does.	2.451	Disagree
	<i>Total weighted mean</i>	2.562	Restrictive

Table 20 Dominance Scale on Restrictiveness: Comparison of Males and Females

Welch's t-test		
Group	Male	Female
Mean	2.56274509802	2.56249999993
SD	0.40443131081	0.45171455086
SEM	0.04386673471	0.05323507035
N	85	72
Intermediate values used in calculations: t = 0.0036 df = 144 standard error of difference = 0.069		
P value and statistical significance: The two-tailed P value equals 0.9972 By conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be not statistically significant. Confidence interval: The mean of Male minus Female equals 0.00024509809 95% confidence interval of this difference: From -0.13609931097 to 0.13658950716		

Table 21 Dominance Scale on Restrictiveness Item Weighted Means: Without Romantic Partner

	Item	Weighted Mean N=92	Verbal Interpretation
2	I try to keep my partner from spending time with opposite sex friends.	2.283	Disagree
4	It bothers me when my partner makes plans without talking to me first.	2.712	Agree
7	My partner should not keep any secrets from me.	2.935	Agree
8	I insist on knowing where my partner is at all times.	2.522	Agree
13	I tend to be jealous.	2.636	Agree
16	I have a right to know everything my partner does.	2.527	Agree
17	It would make me mad if my partner did something I had said not to do.	2.690	Agree
20	I understand there are some things my partner may not want to talk about with me.	1.978	Disagree
32	I have a right to be involved with anything my partner does.	2.413	Disagree
	<i>Total weighted mean</i>	2.522	Restrictive

Table 22 Dominance Scale on Restrictiveness Item Weighted Means: With Romantic Partner

	Item	Weighted Mean N=65	Verbal Interpretation
2	I try to keep my partner from spending time with opposite sex friends.	2.262	Disagree
4	It bothers me when my partner makes plans without talking to me first.	2.708	Agree
7	My partner should not keep any secrets from me.	3.200	Agree
8	I insist on knowing where my partner is at all times.	2.746	Agree
13	I tend to be jealous.	2.923	Agree
16	I have a right to know everything my partner does.	2.562	Agree
17	It would make me mad if my partner did something I had said not to do.	2.977	Agree
20	I understand there are some things my partner may not want to talk about with me.	1.715	Disagree
32	I have a right to be involved with anything my partner does.	2.492	Disagree
	<i>Total weighted mean</i>	2.621	Restrictive

Table 23 Dominance Scale Restrictiveness: Comparison of Respondents with and without Romantic Partner

Welch's t-test		
Group	Without Romantic Partner	With Romantic Commitment
Mean	2.52173913039	2.62051282048
SD	0.38683010964	0.47166728326
SEM	0.04032982683	0.05850312629
N	92	65
Intermediate values used in calculations: t = 1.3901 df = 120 standard error of difference = 0.071		
P value and statistical significance: The two-tailed P value equals 0.1671 By conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be not statistically significant. Confidence interval: The mean of Without Romantic Partner minus With Romantic Commitment equals -0.09877369009 95% confidence interval of this difference: From -0.23946178274 to 0.04191440257		

Table 24 Scale of Interpretation for Total Weighted Means of the Dominance Scale on Disparagement

Range	Verbal Interpretation
1.000 – 1.750	Very non-disparaging
1.751 – 2.500	Non-disparaging
2.501 – 3.250	Disparaging
3.251 – 4.000	Very disparaging

Table 25 Dominance Scale on Disparagement Item Weighted Means: Male

	Item	Weighted Mean N=85	Verbal Interpretation
1	My partner often has good ideas.	2.077	Disagree
5	My partner doesn't have enough sense to make important decisions.	2.229	Disagree
12	I generally consider my partner's interests as much as mine.	2.041	Disagree
22	My partner is a talented person.	1.800	Disagree
23	It's hard for my partner to learn new things.	2.277	Disagree
24	People usually like my partner.	2.053	Disagree
25	My partner makes a lot of mistakes.	2.477	Disagree
26	My partner can handle most things that happen.	2.106	Disagree
27	I sometimes think my partner is unattractive.	1.753	Disagree

28	My partner is basically a good person.	1.765	Disagree
29	My partner doesn't know how to act in public.	2.118	Disagree
	<i>Total weighted mean</i>	2.063	Non-disparaging

Table 26 Dominance Scale on Disparagement Item Weighted Means: Female

	Item	Weighted Mean N=72	Verbal Interpretation
1	My partner often has good ideas.	2.083	Disagree
5	My partner doesn't have enough sense to make important decisions.	2.063	Disagree
12	I generally consider my partner's interests as much as mine.	2.035	Disagree
22	My partner is a talented person.	1.861	Disagree
23	It's hard for my partner to learn new things.	2.118	Disagree
24	People usually like my partner.	1.958	Disagree
25	My partner makes a lot of mistakes.	2.326	Disagree
26	My partner can handle most things that happen.	2.083	Disagree
27	I sometimes think my partner is unattractive.	1.903	Disagree
28	My partner is basically a good person.	1.694	Strongly disagree
29	My partner doesn't know how to act in public.	2.236	Disagree
	<i>Total weighted mean</i>	2.033	Non-disparaging

Table 27 Dominance Scale on Disparagement: Comparison of Males and Females

Welch's t-test		
Group	Male	Female
Mean	2.06310160434	2.03282828289
SD	0.39626938226	0.39110573490
SEM	0.04298144926	0.04609225289
N	85	72
Intermediate values used in calculations: t = 0.4804 df = 151 standard error of difference = 0.063		
P value and statistical significance: The two-tailed P value equals 0.6317 By conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be not statistically significant. Confidence interval: The mean of Male minus Female equals 0.03027332145 95% confidence interval of this difference: From -0.09424749919 to 0.15479414210		

Table 28 Dominance Scale on Disparagement Item Weighted Means: Without Romantic Partner

	Item	Weighted Mean N=92	Verbal Interpretation
1	My partner often has good ideas.	2.207	Disagree
5	My partner doesn't have enough sense to make important decisions.	2.294	Disagree
12	I generally consider my partner's interests as much as mine.	2.136	Disagree
22	My partner is a talented person.	2.000	Disagree
23	It's hard for my partner to learn new things.	2.310	Disagree
24	People usually like my partner.	2.130	Disagree
25	My partner makes a lot of mistakes.	2.457	Disagree
26	My partner can handle most things that happen.	2.179	Disagree
27	I sometimes think my partner is unattractive.	1.935	Disagree
28	My partner is basically a good person.	1.842	Disagree
29	My partner doesn't know how to act in public.	2.223	Disagree
	<i>Total weighted mean</i>	2.156	Non-disparaging

Table 29 Dominance Scale on Disparagement Item Weighted Means: With Romantic Partner

	Item	Weighted Mean N=65	Verbal Interpretation
1	My partner often has good ideas.	1.900	Disagree
5	My partner doesn't have enough sense to make important decisions.	1.954	Disagree
12	I generally consider my partner's interests as much as mine.	1.900	Disagree
22	My partner is a talented person.	1.585	Strongly disagree
23	It's hard for my partner to learn new things.	2.054	Disagree
24	People usually like my partner.	1.839	Disagree
25	My partner makes a lot of mistakes.	2.339	Disagree
26	My partner can handle most things that happen.	1.977	Disagree
27	I sometimes think my partner is unattractive.	1.662	Strongly disagree
28	My partner is basically a good person.	1.577	Strongly disagree
29	My partner doesn't know how to act in public.	2.100	Disagree
	<i>Total weighted mean</i>	1.899	Non-disparaging

Table 30 Dominance Scale on Disparagement: Comparison of Respondents with and without Romantic Partner

Welch's t-test		
Group	Without Romantic Partner	With Romantic Partner
Mean	2.15563241111	1.89860139869
SD	0.35994843776	0.39091315656
SEM	0.03752721880	0.04848680962
N	92	65
Intermediate values used in calculations: t = 4.1921 df = 130 standard error of difference = 0.061		
P value and statistical significance: The two-tailed P value is less than 0.0001 By conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be extremely statistically significant . Confidence interval: The mean of Without Romantic Partner minus With Romantic Partner equals 0.25703101242 95% confidence interval of this difference: From 0.13573085934 to 0.37833116549		

Table 31 Relationship between Divorce Attitudes and Dominance Scale on Authority

Pearson r calculation	
<p>X Values $\Sigma = 548.6$ Mean = 3.494 $\Sigma(X - M_x)^2 = SS_x = 45.325$</p> <p>Y Values $\Sigma = 343.583$ Mean = 2.188 $\Sigma(Y - M_y)^2 = SS_y = 23.655$</p>	<p>X and Y Combined N = 157 $\Sigma(X - M_x)(Y - M_y) = -10.539$</p> <p>R Calculation $r = \Sigma((X - M_x)(Y - M_y)) / \sqrt{((SS_x)(SS_y))}$ $r = -10.539 / \sqrt{((45.325)(23.655))} = -0.3219$</p>
<p>r = -0.3219 The P-Value is .000041. The result is significant at p < .05. There exists a significant moderate inverse relationship between Divorce Attitudes and Dominance Scale on Authority</p>	

Table 32 Relationship between Divorce Attitudes and Dominance Scale on Restrictiveness

Pearson r calculation	
<p>X Values $\Sigma = 548.6$ Mean = 3.494 $\Sigma(X - M_x)^2 = SS_x = 45.325$</p>	<p>X and Y Combined N = 157 $\Sigma(X - M_x)(Y - M_y) = -2.599$</p> <p>R Calculation</p>

Y Values Σ = 402.333 Mean = 2.563 Σ(Y - My) ² = SSy = 28.227	$r = \frac{\sum((X - Mx)(Y - My))}{\sqrt{((SSx)(SSy))}}$ $r = -2.599 / \sqrt{((45.325)(28.227))} = -0.0727$
r = -0.0727 The P-Value is .370193. The result is not significant at p < .05.	

Table 33 Relationship between Divorce Attitudes and Dominance Scale on Disparagement

Pearson r calculation	
X Values Σ = 548.6 Mean = 3.494 Σ(X - Mx) ² = SSx = 45.325 Y Values Σ = 321.727 Mean = 2.049 Σ(Y - My) ² = SSy = 24.087	X and Y Combined N = 157 Σ(X - Mx)(Y - My) = -7.769 R Calculation $r = \frac{\sum((X - My)(Y - Mx))}{\sqrt{((SSx)(SSy))}}$ $r = -7.769 / \sqrt{((45.325)(24.087))} = -0.2351$
r = -0.2351 The P-Value is .00305. The result is significant at p < .05. There exists a significant low inverse relationship between Divorce Attitudes and Dominance Scale on Disparagement	

4. Discussion

It can be seen in Table 2 that for male respondents, “there should be divorce when there are repeated abuses against one spouse or their child” is the item with the highest weighted mean of 4.224 and has a verbal interpretation of *strongly agree*. On the other hand, “there should be divorce when both parties have been living separately for two years” is the item with the lowest weighted mean of 2.824 and has a verbal interpretation of *neutral*. Overall, the total weighted mean is 3.424 with a verbal interpretation of *agree*.

It can be observed in Table 3 that for female respondents, “there should be divorce when there are repeated abuses against one spouse or their child” is the item with the highest weighted mean of 4.542 and has a verbal interpretation of *strongly agree*. However, “there should be divorce when both parties have been living separately for two years” is the item with the lowest weighted mean of 2.986 and has a verbal interpretation of *neutral*. Overall, the total weighted mean is 3.578 with a verbal interpretation of *agree*.

Table 4 presents the comparison of male and female responses and that the females have a higher total weighted mean than the males.

It can be observed in Table 5 that for the respondents without a romantic partner, “there should be divorce when there are repeated abuses against one spouse or their child” is the item with the highest weighted mean of 4.261 and has a verbal interpretation of *strongly agree*. On the other hand, “there should be divorce when both parties have been living separately for two years” is the item with the lowest weighted mean of 2.837 and has a verbal interpretation of *neutral*. Overall, the total weighted mean is 3.460 with a verbal interpretation of *agree*.

It can be seen in Table 6 that for the respondents with a romantic partner, “there should be divorce when there are repeated abuses against one spouse or their child” is the item with the highest weighted mean of 4.524 and has a verbal interpretation of *strongly agree*. However, “there should be divorce when both parties have been living separately for

two years” is the item with the lowest weighted mean of 2.969 and has a verbal interpretation of *neutral*. Overall, the total weighted mean is 3.541 with a verbal interpretation of *agree*.

Table 7 shows the comparison of responses by those with and without a romantic partner and that those with a romantic partner have a higher total weighted mean than those without.

Table 8 presents the overall combined responses of the 157 respondents of this study. The total weighted mean is 3.482 with a verbal interpretation of *agree*.

It can be observed in Table 11 that the male responses to the Dominance Authority subscale, “I often tell my partner how to do something,” is the item with the highest weighted mean of 2.541 with a verbal interpretation of *agree*. On the other hand, “both partners in a relationship should have equal say about decisions,” is the item with the lowest weighted mean of 1.718 with a verbal interpretation of *disagree*. For the male respondents of this study and based on the total weighted mean of 2.204, it can be inferred that they are *non-authoritative*.

It can be seen in Table 12 that the female responses to the Dominance Authority subscale, “if my partner and I can't agree, I usually have the final say,” is the item with the highest weighted mean of 2.639 with a verbal interpretation of *agree*. On the other hand, “both partners in a relationship should have equal say about decisions,” is the item with the lowest weighted mean of 1.500 with a verbal interpretation of *strongly disagree*. For the female respondents of this study and based on the total weighted mean of 2.170, it can be surmised that they are *non-authoritative*.

Based on the Welch's t-test calculation in Table 13, it can be seen that there is no significant difference between the male and female responses with respect to Dominance Authority subscale scores.

It can be observed in Table 14 that the responses of those without a romantic partner to the Dominance Authority subscale, “if my partner and I can't agree, I usually have the final say,” is the item with the highest weighted mean of 2.505 with a verbal interpretation of *agree*. However, “both partners in a relationship should have equal say about decisions,” is the item with the lowest weighted mean of 1.712 with a verbal interpretation of *strongly disagree*. For the respondents of this study without a romantic partner and based on the total weighted mean of 2.220, it can be inferred that they are *non-authoritative*.

It can be observed in Table 15 that the responses of those with a romantic partner to the Dominance Authority subscale, “if my partner and I can't agree, I usually have the final say,” is the item with the highest weighted mean of 2.570 with a verbal interpretation of *agree*. However, “both partners in a relationship should have equal say about decisions,” is the item with the lowest weighted mean of 1.485 with a verbal interpretation of *strongly disagree*. For the respondents of this study with a romantic partner and based on the total weighted mean of 2.144, it can be surmised that they are *non-authoritative*.

According to the Welch's t-test calculation in Table 16, it can be observed that there is no significant difference between the responses of those with and without a romantic partner with respect to Dominance Authority subscale scores.

It can be observed in Table 18 that the male responses to the Dominance Restrictiveness subscale, “my partner should not keep any secrets from me,” is the item with the highest weighted mean of 3.000 with a verbal interpretation of *agree*. On the other hand, “I understand there are some things my partner may not want to talk about with me,” is the item with the lowest weighted mean of 1.971 with a verbal interpretation of *disagree*. For the male respondents of this study and based on the total weighted mean of 2.563, it can be inferred that they are *restrictive*.

It can be seen in Table 19 that the female responses to the Dominance Restrictiveness subscale, “my partner should not keep any secrets from me,” is the item with the highest weighted mean of 3.097 with a verbal interpretation of *agree*. However, “I understand there are some things my partner may not want to talk about with me,” is the item with the lowest weighted mean of 1.750 with a verbal interpretation of *disagree*. For the female respondents of this study and based on the total weighted mean of 2.563, it can be surmised that they are *restrictive*.

Looking at the Welch's t-test calculation in Table 20, it can be seen that there is no significant difference between the male and female responses with respect to Dominance Restrictiveness subscale scores.

It can be observed in Table 21 that the responses of those without a romantic partner to the Dominance Restrictiveness subscale, “my partner should not keep any secrets from me,” is the item with the highest weighted mean of 2.935 with a verbal interpretation of *agree*. On the other hand, “I understand there are some things my partner may not want to

talk about with me,” is the item with the lowest weighted mean of 1.978 with a verbal interpretation of *disagree*. For the respondents of this study without a romantic partner and based on the total weighted mean of 2.522, it can be inferred that they are *restrictive*.

It can be seen in Table 22 that the responses of those with a romantic partner to the Dominance Restrictiveness subscale, “my partner should not keep any secrets from me,” is the item with the highest weighted mean of 3.200 with a verbal interpretation of *agree*. On the other hand, “I understand there are some things my partner may not want to talk about with me,” is the item with the lowest weighted mean of 1.715 with a verbal interpretation of *disagree*. For the respondents of this study with a romantic partner and based on the total weighted mean of 2.621, it can be surmised that they are *restrictive*.

According to the Welch’s t-test calculation in Table 23, it can be observed that there is no significant difference between the responses of those with and without a romantic partner with respect to Dominance Restrictiveness subscale scores.

It can be observed in Table 25 that the male responses to the Dominance Disparagement subscale, “my partner makes a lot of mistakes,” is the item with the highest weighted mean of 2.477 with a verbal interpretation of *disagree*. However, “I sometimes think my partner is unattractive,” is the item with the lowest weighted mean of 1.753 with a verbal interpretation of *disagree*. For the male respondents of this study and based on the total weighted mean of 2.063, it can be inferred that they are *non-disparaging*.

It can be seen in Table 26 that the female responses to the Dominance Disparagement subscale, “my partner makes a lot of mistakes,” is the item with the highest weighted mean of 2.326 with a verbal interpretation of *disagree*. On the other hand, “my partner is basically a good person,” is the item with the lowest weighted mean of 1.694 with a verbal interpretation of *strongly disagree*. For the female respondents of this study and based on the total weighted mean of 2.033, it can be surmised that they are *non-disparaging*.

Based on the Welch’s t-test calculation in Table 27, it can be seen that there is no significant difference between the male and female responses with respect to Dominance Disparagement subscale scores.

It can be observed in Table 28 that the responses of those without a romantic partner to the Dominance Disparagement subscale, “my partner makes a lot of mistakes,” is the item with the highest weighted mean of 2.457 with a verbal interpretation of *disagree*. On the other hand, “my partner is basically a good person,” is the item with the lowest weighted mean of 1.842 with a verbal interpretation of *disagree*. For the respondents of this study without a romantic partner and based on the total weighted mean of 2.156, it can be inferred that they are *non-disparaging*.

It can be seen in Table 29 that the responses of those with a romantic partner to the Dominance Disparagement subscale, “my partner makes a lot of mistakes,” is the item with the highest weighted mean of 2.339 with a verbal interpretation of *disagree*. However, “my partner is basically a good person,” is the item with the lowest weighted mean of 1.577 with a verbal interpretation of *strongly disagree*. For the respondents of this study with a romantic partner and based on the total weighted mean of 1.899, it can be surmised that they are *non-disparaging*.

As can be seen from the Welch’s t-test calculation in Table 30, it can be observed that there is an extremely statistically significant difference between the responses of those with and without a romantic partner with respect to Dominance Disparagement subscale scores. And because the mean of those without a romantic partner is higher, it further be inferred that they are more disparaging than those with a romantic partner.

In Table 31, it can be observed that the Pearson r computation between PDAQ scores and the Dominance Authority subscale scores yielded an r value of -0.3219 with a P-Value is .000041. This implies that there is a significant moderate inverse relationship between the respondents’ PDAQ scores and Dominance Authority subscale scores. This means that for the respondents of this study, as their PDAQ scores increase, their Dominance Authority subscale scores moderately decrease and vice-versa.

In Table 32, it can be observed that the Pearson r computation between PDAQ scores and the Dominance Restrictiveness subscale scores yielded an r value of -0.0727 with a P-Value is .370193. This implies that for the respondents of this study, there is no significant relationship between PDAQ scores and the Dominance Restrictiveness subscale scores.

In Table 33, it can be seen that the Pearson r computation between PDAQ scores and the Dominance Disparagement subscale scores yielded an r value of -0.2351 with a P-Value is .00305. This implies that there is a significant low inverse relationship between the respondents’ PDAQ scores and their Dominance Disparagement subscale scores. This means

that for the respondents of this study, as their PDAQ scores increase, their Dominance Disparagement subscale scores slightly decrease and vice-versa.

5. Conclusion

The PDAQ yielded total weighted means that had verbal interpretations of agree, for both males and females and for those with or without a romantic partner.

With regard to dominance, the respondents' total weighted mean for the subscale of authority found that the respondents were non-authoritative.

With respect to the dominance subscale of disparagement, the respondents' total weighted means found that they were non-disparaging.

Nevertheless, for the dominance subscale of restrictiveness, the respondents' total weighted means showed that they were restrictive for both males and females and for those with or without a romantic partner.

Moreover, an extremely statistically significant difference between the responses of those with and without a romantic partner with respect to Dominance Disparagement subscale scores was established. And because the mean of those without romantic is higher, it can be inferred that the latter are more disparaging than those with a romantic partner.

A significant moderate inverse relationship was found between the respondents' PDAQ and Dominance Authority subscale scores. It can be inferred that for the respondents of this study, as their Dominance Authority subscale scores increase, their PDAQ scores moderately decrease and vice versa.

Furthermore, a significant low inverse relationship between the respondents' PDAQ and their Dominance Disparagement subscale scores was also established. It can be surmised that for the respondents of this study, as their Dominance Disparagement subscale scores increase, their PDAQ scores slightly decrease and vice versa.

Based on these relationships, it would appear that for these respondents, the higher their Dominance is for Authority and Disparagement, the less likely they are to possess an agreeable attitude to the grounds of divorce as set forth by Padilla's bill.

This study is limited by the number of respondents, their variety and the sampling technique used as well as by the researcher-made instrument utilized. Further study is recommended on a larger and more random sample of respondents as well as to explore what other characteristics other than dominance influences attitudes toward divorce.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The author declares no conflict of interest in the conduct of this study.

Statement of ethical approval

The author further states that the ethical standards of research were strictly followed.

Statement of informed consent

The informed consent of all the research participants was obtained, their responses were acquired anonymously and the data gathered was used purely for the purpose of making this study.

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